

Methodology of teaching Chinese languages as a second language to native English speakers. Similarities and differences between Western and Eastern languages.

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ABSTRACT: This article presents opinions and facts about the world's leading languages, English and Chinese. The alphabet and grammar of two major languages are analyzed. Similarities and differences are distinguished and explained with the help of examples. The article discusses basic knowledge and skills for English speakers who are beginning to learn Chinese. English, and Chinese examples are cited.

Keywords: Languages, big group, USA, China, Shan Dynasty, dialects, pinyin, tones, HSK, radicals, verb "to be", similarities, differences.

It is known that there are totally 7 billion people on earth, and they communicate with each other in more than 7,000 languages. There are languages, which are spoken by billions of people, while others are spoken by only one hundred to one hundred and fifty people in the world. Taking into account this factor, languages used for communication are divided into big and small groups. The state languages of countries such as the USA, Spain, China, and France, which have the highest number of speakers in terms of population and the number of state language speakers, are part of a big group. Many people learn these languages because they are widespread on earth.

It's no secret that English speakers are divided into 2 different categories: Those whose native language is English and those who are not native speakers of this language, but have been learning and communicating throughout their lives. For those who belong to two categories, additional language learning is carried out using the language in which they can communicate fluently, that is, English. However, learning some languages can be difficult due to differences in their grammar and sound system. These differences are especially noticeable when it comes to eastern languages. Languages such as Japanese, Chinese, and Korean are very different from English in terms of their sound system, as well as their grammar. We will consider these differences on the example of the Chinese language.

China is distinguished by its large population. China is one of the world's leading countries in terms of the world economy and its share in production. For these reasons, learning the Chinese language has become more and more popular in recent years. The Chinese language has a history of 6,000 years, and it was first found in the sources of the Shan Dynasty. Different characters are used to express each word in the Chinese language. There are more than a few thousand of these characters, and in order to communicate or read books in normal life, it is necessary to recognize 2-2.5 thousand characters on average. Like other languages, Chinese has several dialects. The diversity of these dialects also depends on the large territory of the country. Although the dialects are different, there is no great difference between their written forms of communication. There are 3 types of written Chinese language, they are divided into traditional, simplified and informal. Nowadays, people living in China and learning this language as a foreign language use its simplified form.

The transcription of Chinese words using the traditional alphabet is called "pinyin". The pinyin system of the Chinese language is mainly used by those who know the Western (English) alphabet well and those who have just started learning the Chinese language:

中国 – zhōngguó (China)

学生 – xuésheng (student)

The pinyin of these words are zhōngguó and xuésheng. By memorizing the pinyin of each word, the students' ability to fully understand the topic of the conversation is formed.

In Chinese, there is also the term tone, which can be used to pronounce words correctly.

In Chinese, tones are expressed in 4 ways:

Shū (书 - book) – 1st tone;

Rén (人 - human) – 2nd tone;

Wǒ (我 - I) – 3rd tone;

Xièxie (谢谢 - thanks) – 4th tone.

The pronunciation of words in these tones differs from each other and serves to create the necessary context in communication. By distinguishing tones and pronouncing words according to the rules of tones, it is possible to raise the speaking ability to a higher level.

During the study of the Chinese language, students are divided according to their level of knowledge. Chinese language learners first prepare using the HSK1 book. The concepts of tone

and pinyin mentioned above are also explained to students in HSK1. There are levels of Chinese from HSK1 to HSK6.

One of the easiest ways to learn Chinese words is learning radicals. Radicals serve as the basis for making words. The Chinese language has a total of 214 radicals. The main role in the creation of radicals is played by the appearance of what radical represents:

山 (shān) – mountain

儿 (ér) – legs

目 (mù) – eye

As can be seen from the above examples, each radical is memorized by analogy with the word it represents. More precisely, the appearance of the 儿 (ér) really resembles human legs. We can compare the 3 parts in the 山 (shān) to the 3 rocks of the mountain.

Those who study Chinese language learn by comparing its words and grammar rules with English. Although the pronunciation of the words is not the same, some grammatical rules are similar. We can see this in the example of the English word “to be”. In Chinese, the sentence “I am a doctor” is expressed like that:

我是医生。(Wǒ shì yīshēng) – I **am** a doctor.

In this example, “to be” is expressed using the word “是” (shì). It corresponds to “am” in English. The difference is that while in English “to be” is expressed in 3 types (am, is, are), only “是” (shì) is used in Chinese.

There are many examples of such similarities and differences. After all, two of them are official languages of countries in two different regions. For this reason, it is natural that there is a greater difference between them than others.

In conclusion, it can be said that in learning Eastern languages, importance should be paid to several factors mentioned above, and useful methods should be applied in practice. In addition, we can see some aspects of Eastern languages, including Chinese, that are not found in Western languages. In particular, the alphabet system has great differences. However, some grammatical rules are exactly repeated in this language. By studying all aspects, the learner can achieve the desired result.

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